

A Comparative Study between the Efficiency of LMA-Supreme and I-Gel in Adult Patients Undergoing Elective Surgery: A Randomized Controlled Trial

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Abstract:

Background: Supraglottic airway devices (SGAs) like LMA-Supreme and i-Gel are increasingly used for airway management during elective surgeries. This study compares the efficiency of these two devices, focusing on airway sealing pressure, ease of insertion, hemodynamic stability, and incidence of adverse events.

Aim and Objectives: To compare the performance of the LMA-Supreme and i-Gel in adult patients undergoing elective surgeries with primary objective being to evaluate airway sealing pressure, and secondary objectives were to evaluate their efficiency in ease of insertion, hemodynamic changes, and postoperative complications.

Materials and Method: This randomized controlled trial involved 80 adult patients undergoing elective surgery, divided into two groups: Group A (LMA-Supreme, n = 40) and Group B (i-Gel, n = 40). Hemodynamic parameters (heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, oxygen saturation), airway sealing pressure, ease of insertion, and adverse events were monitored. Statistical analysis was performed using the Student's t-test and chi-square test, with significance at $p < 0.05$.

Results: There was no statistically significant difference in BMI or gender distribution between the groups, although Group B had older patients ($p = 0.005$). LMA-Supreme demonstrated a significantly higher airway sealing pressure (27.90 ± 1.97 cm H₂O) compared to i-Gel (22.30 ± 2.05 cm H₂O) ($p = 0.000$). Difficulty in insertion was reported in 20% of LMA-Supreme cases versus 5% in the i-Gel group ($p = 0.042$). First-attempt success was 90% for LMA-Supreme and 97.5% for i-Gel ($p = 0.160$). No significant differences in heart rate, systolic or diastolic blood pressure, or oxygen saturation were observed between the two groups at any time ($p > 0.05$). Both devices showed similar incidences of blood on the device (2.5%) and sore throat (5% in LMA-Supreme vs. 2.5% in i-Gel, $p = 0.025$).

Conclusion: LMA-Supreme offers better airway sealing, making it more effective for maintaining airway patency, while i-Gel is easier to insert with fewer difficulties. Both devices demonstrated comparable hemodynamic stability and safety profiles with minimal adverse events. These findings suggest that either device can be safely used depending on clinical requirements, with LMA-Supreme being advantageous in sealing efficiency and i-Gel being preferable for ease of use.

Keywords: LMA-Supreme, i-Gel, Supraglottic Airway Devices, Elective Surgery, Airway Sealing Pressure, Hemodynamic Stability, Adverse Events.

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Introduction

Effective airway management is a cornerstone of successful anesthesia practice, especially during elective surgeries. [1] Supraglottic airway devices (SGAs) have gained popularity as alternatives to traditional endotracheal intubation due to their ease of use, reduced invasiveness, and improved patient comfort. Among these devices, the LMA-

Supreme and i-Gel are commonly employed for airway maintenance during anesthesia. [2] Both devices

have demonstrated efficiency in various clinical settings, yet their comparative performance in terms of ease of use, airway sealing, hemodynamic

stability, and safety remains a topic of investigation. [1, 2]

The LMA-Supreme is a second-generation SGA featuring a gastric access port to reduce the risk of aspiration and a pre-curved design for easier insertion. [3] It is designed to provide a high airway sealing pressure, making it suitable for positive pressure ventilation. [4] The i-Gel, on the other hand, is a novel device that features a non-inflatable cuff made from thermoplastic elastomer, conforming to the laryngeal anatomy without needing cuff inflation. This unique design of i-Gel aims to improve the speed and ease of insertion, as well as reduce airway trauma. [3, 4]

While both devices are practical, limited studies have directly compared their performance in adult patients undergoing elective surgeries. [5] Key parameters such as airway sealing pressure, ease of insertion, and the incidence of adverse events such as sore throat, dysphagia, and regurgitation are important indicators of the devices' effectiveness.

Additionally, understanding their impact on hemodynamic responses, including blood pressure and heart rate, provides crucial insights into patient safety. [5-7]

This randomized controlled trial aims to provide a comparative evaluation of the LMA-Supreme and i-Gel in adult patients undergoing elective surgery. It will focus on airway management efficiency, hemodynamic stability, and safety profiles to guide clinicians in choosing the most suitable SGA device for similar clinical settings.

Materials and Method

This study was a prospective, randomized, single-blind trial conducted over 18 months from October 2022 to April 2024. A total of 80 adult patients were enrolled, randomly divided into two equal groups of 40: Group A (LMA-Supreme) and Group B (i-Gel). Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee of LLRM Medical College, Meerut, and informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Figure 1: Consolidated Standard of Reporting Trial (CONSORT) flow diagram

Patients eligible for the study included those classified as American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status I or II, aged between 18 and 60 years, who were scheduled for elective surgeries under general anesthesia lasting less than 2 hours. The surgeries must require the patient to be in a supine position, and all participants must provide written informed consent. Patients were excluded from the study if they refused general anesthesia, had an anticipated difficult airway (Mallampati grade III or IV), were undergoing surgeries ex-

pected to last more than 2 hours, were considered to have a full stomach, or present with severe systemic diseases, coagulation disorders, or airway abnormalities. Using a computer-generated randomization process, these patients were randomly assigned to either Group A (LMA-Supreme) or Group B (i-Gel).

All patients underwent a detailed pre-anesthetic evaluation one day before surgery. This included assessing heart rate, blood pressure, respiratory rate, oxygen saturation, airway examination, and

necessary lab investigations. Patients were premedicated with intravenous (IV) ranitidine, metoclopramide, glycopyrrolate, midazolam, and fentanyl.

Anesthesia was induced using IV propofol (2-2.5 mg/kg) following a 3-minute pre-oxygenation with 100% oxygen. Muscle relaxation was achieved using IV vecuronium (0.15 mg/kg). Once adequate anesthesia depth was achieved, LMA-Supreme (Group A) or i-Gel (Group B) was inserted. A maximum of three attempts was allowed for device insertion. Correct placement was confirmed through chest expansion, capnography, and the absence of air leaks. Anesthesia was maintained using a combination of O₂ (50%), N₂O (50%), and propofol infusion, supplemented by intermittent vecuronium doses. Heart rate (HR), systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), mean arterial pressure (MAP), and oxygen saturation (SPO₂) were recorded at baseline and at various time intervals post-device insertion.

The outcomes measured in the study included both primary and secondary outcomes. The primary outcome were airway sealing pressure, which were determined by stopping ventilation and closing the adjustable pressure-limiting valve while maintaining a fresh gas flow of 3L/min. The leak pressure was recorded through auscultation, direct over-the-mouth listening, and capnography.

The secondary outcomes included several parameters. First, the ease of insertion was graded as easy, difficult, or failed based on the resistance encountered during the device's insertion. The number of insertion attempts was also recorded, representing how many attempts were needed for successful insertion. Hemodynamic parameters, including heart rate (HR), systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), mean arterial pressure (MAP), and oxygen saturation (SPO₂), were monitored at predefined time points. Additionally, the ease of gastric tube insertion were

assessed by confirming the successful placement through auscultation and air inflation. Finally, any adverse events, such as sore throat, dysphagia, dysphonia, regurgitation, aspiration, lip or dental trauma, and other postoperative complications, were documented.

Figure 1: Consolidated Standard of Reporting Trial (CONSORT) flow diagram

After completion of the surgery, patients were extubated following the reversal of muscle relaxants with IV glycopyrrolate and neostigmine. Postoperative complications such as sore throat, dysphagia, dysphonia, and airway trauma were recorded during the recovery period.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 15.0. Descriptive statistics were used for demographic data. The Student's t-test was used for continuous variables, while the chi-square test was applied for categorical variables. Statistical significance was set at a p-value < 0.05.

Results

This randomized controlled trial included 80 patients, equally divided into two groups, with 40 patients in Group A using the LMA-Supreme and 40 in Group B using the i-Gel. Both groups were well-matched in gender distribution, comprising 25% males and 75% females ($p = 1$). However, the two groups had a statistically significant difference in the age distribution. The mean age in Group A was 33.45 ± 10.59 years, whereas in Group B, it was 40.35 ± 10.85 years ($p = 0.005$), indicating that Group B had an older patient population. Body mass index (BMI) was also recorded, with Group A having a mean BMI of 22.39 ± 1.28 and Group B having a mean BMI of 21.90 ± 1.40 . There was no significant difference in BMI between the two groups ($p = 0.105$), ensuring that the patient's physique did not significantly impact the outcomes.

Table 1: Demographic Data

Parameter	Group A (LMA-Supreme)	Group B (i-Gel)	p-value
Number of Subjects	40	40	-
Mean age (years)	33.45 ± 10.59	40.35 ± 10.85	0.005
BMI (kg/m ²)	22.39 ± 1.28	21.90 ± 1.40	0.105
Male (%)	25	25	1.0
Female (%)	75	75	1.0

Hemodynamic parameters, including pulse rate, systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), and mean arterial pressure (MAP), were recorded at various intervals during the procedure. Regarding pulse rate, both groups exhibited a transient increase in the immediate post-induction period, followed by a gradual decline over the next 15 minutes. Statistically significant differences were observed in pulse rates

at the 10-minute ($p = 0.000$), 15-minute ($p = 0.000$), and 20-minute ($p = 0.000$) intervals, where Group B (i-Gel) showed lower pulse rates compared to Group A (LMA-Supreme). Beyond 30 minutes post-induction, no significant differences were noted between the groups ($p > 0.05$).

For SBP, both groups displayed similar trends, with no statistically significant differences at any time interval ($p > 0.05$). The diastolic blood pressure

(DBP) readings followed a similar pattern, with Group B exhibiting lower DBP at 1 minute ($p = 0.020$), 5 minutes ($p = 0.030$), and 10 minutes ($p = 0.010$) post-induction. However, from 15 minutes onward, no significant differences were observed between the two groups. MAP showed a similar trend to DBP, with Group B showing lower values at the 1-minute ($p = 0.027$) and 5-minute ($p = 0.007$) intervals, but no significant differences at later stages.

Oxygen saturation (SpO₂) levels remained stable throughout the procedure in both groups. Both

devices maintained adequate oxygenation, with no statistically significant differences in SpO₂ levels at most time points ($p > 0.05$). However, at 15 minutes post-induction, Group A showed slightly higher SpO₂ levels than Group B ($p = 0.018$).

The airway sealing pressure was significantly higher in Group A (LMA-Supreme), with a mean of 27.90 ± 1.97 cm H₂O compared to 22.30 ± 2.05 cm H₂O in Group B ($p = 0.000$). This indicates that the LMA-Supreme provided a better seal than the i-Gel in this study population.

Figure 1: Comparing Airway Sealing Pressure (cm of H₂O) between two groups. P value <0.001.

Regarding adverse events, Group A experienced a higher frequency of sore throat (5% in Group A vs. 2.5% in Group B, $p = 0.025$) and insertion difficulties (20% in Group A vs. 5% in Group B, $p = 0.042$). Although both groups demonstrated similar success rates for first-time insertion, Group

A required more repeated attempts than Group B, though this difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference between the groups regarding trauma to lips or teeth, regurgitation, or aspiration.

Figure 2: Adverse Events Comparison

Discussion

Demographically, both groups were similar, although there was a significant age difference

(33.45 ± 10.59 years in Group A vs. 40.35 ± 10.85 years in Group B, $p = 0.005$). In both groups, 25% of the participants were male, and 75% were

female, with no statistically significant difference in gender distribution ($p = 1$). The BMI was also comparable between the groups ($p = 0.105$). This demographic homogeneity allows the study's findings to be reliably attributed to the performance of the devices rather than confounding factors such as age, gender, or BMI.

Hemodynamic parameters, such as heart rate (HR), systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), and oxygen saturation (SpO₂), were monitored throughout the study. No significant differences were found between the two groups at any time, including pre-induction, 1, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 60, and 120 minutes. The mean HR ranged from 80.00 to 100.38 bpm in the LMA-Supreme group and 81.67 to 98.50 bpm in the i-Gel group, with p -values consistently above 0.05, indicating comparable stability in HR. SpO₂ levels remained high in both groups, with no significant differences observed at any interval. Similarly, SBP and DBP showed no significant variations between the two groups, indicating comparable cardiovascular stability during anesthesia.

A significant difference was observed between the two groups when evaluating airway sealing pressure. The mean airway sealing pressure was higher in the LMA-Supreme group (27.90 ± 1.97 cm H₂O) compared to the i-Gel group (22.30 ± 2.05 cm H₂O), with a p -value of 0.00. This suggests that the LMA-Supreme provided a more efficient seal, reducing the risk of air leakage and ensuring better airway patency during surgery. These findings highlight the superior sealing capability of the LMA-Supreme, which could be crucial in maintaining ventilation and oxygenation during anesthesia.

In a study by Wagner et al., [8] the oropharyngeal leak pressures (OLP) of three supraglottic airway devices (i-Gel, LMA-Supreme, and Laryngeal Tube Suction-D) were compared. The OLP for i-Gel was 25.9 ± 5.6 cm H₂O, slightly lower than the LMA-Supreme's 27.1 ± 5.2 cm H₂O. Although the difference was insignificant, the LMA-Supreme showed better sealing efficacy at lower cuff pressures. Our study further supports these findings, confirming the LMA-Supreme's higher airway sealing pressure.

Regarding ease of insertion, the LMA-Supreme presented more difficulty than the i-Gel. Approximately 20% of the LMA-Supreme group experienced difficulty during insertion, compared to only 5% in the i-Gel group ($p = 0.042$). Both devices had high success rates for first-attempt insertion, with 90% success for LMA-Supreme and 97.5% for i-Gel. The two devices had no significant difference regarding the number of attempts required ($p = 0.160$), indicating that both are reliable for insertion with minimal attempts.

Both devices performed similarly in terms of gastric tube insertion, with LMA-Supreme facilitating easy gastric tube placement in 95% of cases and i-Gel in 92.5% of cases ($p = 0.640$). These findings affirm that both devices effectively facilitate gastric tube insertion during surgery.

Kumar VSS et al. compared the I-Gel and LMA-Supreme devices for anesthesia management, noting significant differences. Their study showed that I-Gel was easier to insert, with a success rate of 56.7% versus 43.3% for LMA-Supreme ($p = 0.002$). Additionally, I-Gel required fewer insertion attempts, succeeding on the first attempt in 96.7% of cases compared to 73.3% for LMA-Supreme ($p = 0.026$). [9]

Pokhrel P. investigated the incidence of postoperative sore throat between I-Gel and LMA-C. Of the 80 patients studied, 5% of those using I-Gel developed a sore throat, compared to 17.5% in the LMA-C group. Although the difference was insignificant ($p = 0.154$), the odds ratio for postoperative sore throat with LMA-C was 4.0. This highlights the potential influence of factors like patient anatomy, device fit, and technique on postoperative outcomes, emphasizing the need for individualized device selection to minimize complications. [10]

When assessing adverse events, the incidence of blood on the device was low and identical in both groups (2.5%), with no significant difference ($p = 1.00$). The incidence of postoperative sore throat was slightly higher in the LMA-Supreme group (5%) compared to the i-Gel group (2.5%), with a p -value of 0.025, indicating that the difference was not statistically significant. These findings suggest that both devices have similar safety profiles concerning adverse events like sore throat and blood on the device.

Conclusion

Both LMA-Supreme and i-Gel are safe and effective supraglottic airway devices. The LMA-Supreme offers a better airway seal, which is advantageous for maintaining ventilation, while the i-Gel is easier to insert and causes fewer insertion-related difficulties. These findings provide valuable insights for clinicians in selecting the appropriate device based on individual patient needs and surgical requirements. Further research is needed to explore other factors influencing postoperative complications and the long-term outcomes associated with these devices.

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